

Optimizing high-rate algae pond for resource recovery from municipal wastewater

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Abstract

The study focuses on optimising high-rate algae ponds (HRAP) for resource recovery from municipal wastewater. The research aims to optimise operational parameters such as hydraulic retention time (HRT) and to assess the option of sludge return, to maximise algal biomass production while meeting effluent standards. For this, an intensive measurement campaign on a pilot HRAP in Ajdovščina, Slovenia, was performed, which will be used to calibrate a mathematical model to simulate algae-bacteria dynamics. Measurements were performed from 2019 to 2025. The measurements from 2019 to 2024 are taken at single operational mode, i.e., at HRT of 35 days, while in 2025 the campaign was conducted under two different HRT, 35 and 10 days. Monitoring results from 2019 to 2024 indicated variability in treatment performance; however, there was efficient removal of BOD₅ and NH₄-N despite fluctuations in inflow concentrations. The results from 2025 indicate that HRT can be as low as 10 days to achieve acceptable efficiency for BOD removal. However, the concentration of bacteria-microalgae biomass was expectedly lower. There was a clear need for optimisation, particularly in increasing bioactive biomass in the HRAP through, for example, sludge return and varying HRT.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

HRAP, bacteria-microalgae, nature-based solutions, modelling, technology optimization

INTRODUCTION

Nature-based solutions (NBS) have been identified as an important measure to enable resource-oriented wastewater management in addressing climate change challenges (Atanasova et al., 2021). Algal technologies, as one type of NBS, have shown great potential in wastewater treatment, providing several benefits. Microalgae can effectively absorb nutrients from wastewater, enhance CO₂ sequestration, and increase dissolved oxygen levels in water through the photosynthetic activity of microalgal cells (Qi et al., 2021). In addition to improving wastewater treatment efficiency, this approach also enables the valorisation of wastewater by producing valuable biomass that can be converted into eco-friendly bioproducts, supporting the circular bioeconomy and promoting sustainable resource management (Kumar et al., 2022).

The high-rate algal pond (HRAP) is the most common full-scale implementation of algal wastewater treatment systems. Compared to conventional activated sludge treatment, HRAP systems require a larger surface area to provide sufficient light for algal growth and longer hydraulic retention times (HRT) of up to 20 days. Maintaining the vitality of the algae-bacterial community in these systems is essential for efficient wastewater treatment and desired biomass production. Models of bacteria-microalgae dynamics can greatly assist in controlling process conditions and understanding the underlying mechanisms, ultimately leading to optimal performance.

Over the years, these models have evolved from simple steady-state descriptions, where variables such as nitrogen, carbon, phosphorus, and light intensity were considered constant over time and microalgae growth was described as a function of single factors (Aslan and Kapdan, 2006), to complex dynamic models that account for multiple factors and interactions. Their structure is often based on the activated sludge models (ASM) (Henze et al., 2006) and allows for the simulation of

changing environmental conditions and their impact on microalgae and bacteria growth. One of the most comprehensive models developed for HRAPs is the BIO_ALGAE model (Solimeno et al., 2017), which incorporates a wide range of biochemical processes and environmental factors.

The research aims to optimize operational parameters, such as hydraulic retention time (HRT) and sludge retention time (SRT), in a pilot-scale HRAP receiving first-stage treated municipal wastewater, to maximise algal biomass production while meeting effluent requirements. To this end, we present the results of a measurement campaign on a pilot HRAP, which will be used to calibrate a mathematical model of algae-bacteria dynamics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pilot high-rate algal pond

HRAP pilot plant is situated at a municipal WWTP in Ajdovščina, Slovenia (45°52'32.2" N, 13°54'21.4" E). HRAP volume is 3 m³ and surface area is 12.7 m². It is continuously mixed with a paddlewheel (Škufca et al., 2021). The HRAP was fed with the effluent from the primary settler of the WWTP Ajdovščina in a semi-continuous manner exchanging 10% of its volume (300 L) every 3 days resulting in HRT and SRT of 35 days. The effluent from HRAP is directed to a conical sedimentation tank equipped with ultrasound transducer to enhance algae sedimentation (range 50 m, power 12 W, with dual core multi frequency technology, 20–200 kHz, LG SONIC, The Netherlands). Wastewater treatment in the HRAP system is provided by a microbial community mostly consisting of microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Pediastrum boryanum*, *Skeletonema subsalsum*, *Scenedesmus opoliensis*, *Homoeothrix varians* and other native microalgae and bacteria.

Figure 1. Pilot high -rate algal pond at municipal wastewater treatment plant in Ajdovščina, Slovenia.

Water quality parameters at the inflow, HRAP and outflow were monitored weekly during growing season (May/June – October) from 2019 till 2024 and two times a week in 2025. Grab samples of inflow, in the HRAP, and outflow were monitored for total suspended solids (TSS), settleability, BOD₅, COD, total phosphorous, ortophosphate, total nitrogen, ammonia, nitrites and nitrates. In HRAP, pH, electroconductivity, temperature, dissolved oxygen and TSS were measured on-site and the content of chlorophyll-*a* was analysed. In 2019, 2020 and 2024 HRT was maintained predominantly to 35 days. In 2025 the HRAP was operated under two HRT, 3 months (May, June and July) at HRT 30 days and two months (August, September) at HRT 10 days.

Conceptual model of the HRAP

To analyse various impacts on HRAP operation, a mathematical model is proposed, composed of 16 state variables, of which 8 soluble compounds and 4 particulate, 11 processes, and many kinetic and stoichiometric parameters. A simplified conceptual model is presented in Figure 2. The model comprises heterotrophic and autotrophic bacteria and microalgae processes (growth, endogenous respiration and decay), chemical equilibrium reactions, hydrolysis of slowly biodegradable organic matter. The processes are formulated using Monod kinetics and include influences by temperature and light, and wastewater and return sludge inflow. After model calibration on the results presented in this study the model will be used to simulate HRAP operation (1) under different HRT values and (2) under different SRT values. HRT values will be controlled by increasing/decreasing the inflow and SRT by controlling the sludge recycling and sludge wasting.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of the HRAP system with description of the state variables

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HRAP operation

According to the results from 2019 to 2024 (Figure 3), when the HRAP was operated at HRT of predominantly 35 days, there is high variability in HRAP treatment performance; however, BOD_5 and NH_4-N are relatively efficiently removed despite high fluctuations in inflow concentration. TSS in the HRAP was maintained between 350 and 600 mg/l contributed by algae-bacteria biomass. PO_4-P was efficiently removed from June to July during active algae growth, while in October under decreasing daylight nutrient removal was decreased.

Figure 3. Performance of HRAP during growing season between 2019-2024. Average and standard deviation is given.

The results from the measuring campaign in 2025, when the HRAP was operated at two HRT, 35 and 10 days we can observe that the BOD removal efficiency is similar in both operation modes (Figure 4). However, TSS and consequently the concentration of algal biomass was significantly lower at HRT of 10 days, which affected nutrient removal efficiency and the production of biomass, which is one of the optimization goals. Besides lower HRT, weather conditions affected the lower biomass production, such as less sunlight and rainfall. An obvious upgrade of the present system is sludge return to maintain higher concentration of algal-bacterial biomass in the HRAP.

Figure 4. Performance of HRAP during growing season in 2025 under two HRT, 35 days and 10 days.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Intensive monitoring campaign of a HRAP pilot plant was conducted. The results reveal expected behaviour of the HRAP and present a solid data base for calibrating a mathematical algae-bacterial model, conceptually presented in this research. According to the results there is an obvious need for optimizing the HRAP operation in terms of increasing and stabilizing the amount of algal-bacterial biomass in the reactor. The final optimization goal is achieving the highest algae concentration at the lowest HRT, which guides the future steps within this research: (1) calibrating the mathematical model to simulate the dynamics of algae and bacteria in the reactor under different conditions including the biomass response to sludge return, by performing simulations with different SRT values (2) upgrading the pilot HRAP with sludge return according to the model results and finally (3) final optimization of the HRAP and the model.

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